

RehabMove 2018: METABOLIC COST OF DAILY ACTIVITIES IN PEOPLE WITH LOWER LIMB AMPUTATION - A STUDY PROTOCOL

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PURPOSE: People with lower limb amputation (LLA) have higher metabolic costs for walking compared to able bodied persons. A more proximal amputation and a faster walking speed are factors increasing these metabolic costs. For other activities of daily living (ADL) relevant data is very limited. To create an individualized evidence-based rehabilitation program for patients with a LLA, understanding the metabolic cost of multiple ADL, in the context of peak physical capacity, is a requirement. Based on these individualized data, the relative metabolic costs of ADL can be determined and help to set functional and realistic goals of exercise and training activities to improve physical capacity.

METHOD: A search process took place where literature is searched about the remaining functionality and ADL which are representative for people with a LLA. Besides that, discussions have taken place with rehabilitation specialists.

RESULTS: A protocol is developed which consists of ten different -standardized- components of physical fitness and the metabolic costs standardized- ADL. Tests will be conducted over two days. Day 1: a health questionnaire, Range of Motion test (ROM), strength test, Berg Balance Scale, VO₂-peak test (including resting metabolism). Day 2: 6-Minutes Walking Test (6MWT), Timed Up & Go Test (TU>), Stairclimbing test (SCT), submaximal cycling test, Glitter ADL-Test and the Floor Transfer Test (FTT). During these tests, data on (relative) oxygen uptake, energy cost, perceived exertion and heartrate will be determined.

CONCLUSION: A protocol was developed to obtain individualized (relative) metabolic cost of standardized ADL in LLA. Next, this protocol will be tested in LLA on feasibility, reliability and validity.